

SOURCES AND RESERVES OF IMPORT SUBSTITUTION DRINKING PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: . One of the solutions to the problem of sustainable economic growth is the development of local production, which will help reduce imports. From this point of view, the organization of import-substituting industries in Uzbekistan and on this basis to ensure economic growth in the country is the basis of economic policy and forward-looking development strategies implemented in our country. Therefore, this article analyzes the approaches to the development of import-substituting industries.

Keywords. Sustainable development, economic growth, imports, exports, import-substituting industries, industries, technological composition of industry

Introduction

According to the World Bank, the index of foreign trade conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2008-2018 ranged from 0.23 to 0.28. At present, the share of imports in industrial products is 37.0-40.0% [1]. At the end of 2019, the foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 42.2 billion US dollars. USD, which is 8.3 bln. USD more than in the same period of the last year. USD (growth rate - 26.2%). The share of finished products with high added value in exports remains low. In particular, in 2019 the main share of the country's exports will be products made of precious and semi-precious metals - 5.1 billion. USD (28.5% of total exports), services - 3.6 bln. USD (19.9%), energy carriers - 2.5 bln. USD (14.1%), textile products - 1.6 bln. USD (9.1%), food products - 1.5 bln. USD (8.5%), non-ferrous metals and their products - 951.3 mln. USD (5.3%), chemical products and products made from them - 876.9 mln. USD (4.9%), ferrous metals and flour products - 349.6 mln. USD (2%) [2]. Explaining the role and importance of import substitution in strengthening the national position of the foreign economy in international trade relations from the methodological point of view: import substitution; import substitution as an economic process; It is proposed to formulate three opposing definitions of import substitution as an economic policy of the state [3].

An import-substituting economic category is a model for the rapid replacement of imported goods in accordance with the laws of development of the international division of labor and the principles of competition and economic efficiency, in order to stimulate economic growth and structural change.

Substitution of imports as an economic process will increase the production of local goods, which are distinguished by their high level of competitiveness and economic efficiency in comparison with imported goods, increase consumption and expand its potential for future export.

The government's long-term policy of approving and improving the volume of imports by substituting imports as the state's economic policy, encouraging the development of local producers and indirectly regulating imports through protectionist means.

Level of study of the topic. Despite the urgency of the problem of organizing the production of import-substituting and, on this basis, ensuring economic growth in the national economy, this problem has not been studied in detail. Some aspects of ensuring economic growth in the country on the basis of the organization of import-substituting industries J.M. Keynes, J. Itwell, R. ; It is reflected in the scientific works of foreign scholars such as Prebish. In the scientific works of these economists, industrial policy based on the organization of import-substituting industries and, on this basis, the issues of ensuring economic growth in the national economy are considered from the point of view of market economy conditions.

It should be noted that the economic reforms and processes currently underway in the former Soviet republics are in many ways similar. Therefore, if we talk about the economy of the transition period of the Russian Federation, the issues of import substitution are discussed by L.I. Encouraging economic growth in Abalkin's works, S.D. Bodrunov to improve the conditions for the application of economic sanctions against the Russian Federation, AP Kireev to improve the conditions of the country's foreign trade, P. A. Kadochnikov The conditions of the economic situation in the country after 1998 [5], T. M. Isachenko EU Trade Policy, A.P. Terekhova Competitiveness of Industrial Enterprises, N.A. Suchkova, food sector of the country, OV Starovoitova looked at the conditions of the small open economy from the point of view. Along with Shu, K.A. Gulin, E.A. Mazilov, AP While the Yermolovs see import substitution as a means of enhancing the socio-economic development of the regions, V.K. Faltzman considers the organization of import substitution production in the new geopolitical situation, O.B. Berezinskaya and A.L. While Vedev draws attention to the fact that the development of Russian industry depends on imports, E.V. In her research, Volkodavova sees the replacement of imports in terms of the country's integration into the system of world economic relations [6].

Among the economists of our country are HP Abulkasimov, AV Vahabov, TT Juraev, AA Ulmasov, AV Vahobov, SV Chepel [7], RR Khasanov, Sh. F. Yuldashev, FT Egamberdiev, MA Mamatov [8] and others can cite relevant research in this area.

Research methodology. Methods such as statistical and econometric analysis, generalization, grouping, classification, economic-mathematical modeling, comparative analysis and comparison were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. S.D. In his research, Bodrunov combines the concept of import substitution as a strategy and industrial policy, and states that –substitution is a strategy of protecting local producers by substituting imported industrial goods and technologies for national products, and the state and industry by protecting industry. It aims to increase the competitiveness of local products in exchange for the development of new value-added products, increase their efficiency and encourage the modernization of production. In this case, in any case, it is necessary not to try to increase the added value by any means and means - such an approach will lead to an unreasonable increase in production costs, prolong the production cycle and leave it behind. Such a comprehensive definition of import substitution allowed SD Bodrunov to identify a number of targets, which include, first of all, the issues of increasing the competitiveness of local products.

In order to determine the main features and forms of import substitution, in our opinion, we need to identify some of its specific features. First, import-substituting production can partially or completely squeeze out imported products from the domestic market. From this point of view, it is necessary to differentiate between partial or full import substitution. Partial import substitution involves the production of similar imported products, according to which the imported product is partially squeezed out of the domestic market. In this case, the replacement of imports will allow to supply a part of the domestic market, which was previously filled with imported products, with local goods.

Full import substitution implies the organization of the production of imported goods in such a way that local products, due to their competitive advantages, completely squeeze out imported products from the domestic market. Second, the establishment of import-substituting production can be done with the use of local and imported production resources. It should be borne in mind that foreign factors of production (raw materials and technical equipment of enterprises) can be used in the organization of import-substituting production. From this point of view, it is necessary to distinguish between primary and secondary

import substitution. Primary import substitution is the organization of the production of imported products using foreign (import) factors of production (production equipment, raw materials, labor resources, etc.). Secondary import substitution is the use of foreign production equipment, foreign raw materials, and comparative advantages of the country, while the use of high-yield domestic products is the main source of imports. Third, the substitution of imports can also be characterized by the industry, that is, it covers certain sectors and industries of the national economy, in which the production of previously imported products is carried out. This, in turn, can be industrial or agricultural. We must not lose sight of the fact that import substitution can cover all important sectors of the national economy. It depends on the level and comparative advantages of the country's factors of development. The economic literature pays little attention to the sectoral description of import substitution, with much of the published research focusing on import substitution of industrial products. If import substitution exists in industry, then the right question arises as to why such a strategy may not be pursued in agriculture, services, construction, and so on. Thus, the following can be emphasized:

Import substitution as a strategy for the development of the national economy involves the organization of domestic production of previously imported goods, as a result of which the import of such goods is partially or completely abandoned;

partial and full import substitution differs in the degree of squeezing out of imported goods similar to the domestic market;

in the process of organizing import substitution production, it is expedient to separate primary and secondary import substitution according to the level of use of local and foreign production resources;

According to the description of the industry, import substitution can be industrial, agricultural or complex (mixed). Another important aspect of choosing import-substituting forms and types of economic growth is to identify priorities for the path of extensive and intensive development. The methodological basis for the division of import-substituting economic growth into extensive and intensive types is the macroeconomic theory of extended reproduction. In fact, in any economy, the extensive and intensive forms of economic growth are closely intertwined and intertwined. However, it should be borne in mind that in different countries and socio-economic systems, extensive and intensive economic growth factors are applied in different combinations and in certain proportions. For example, the growth of the means of production and

the labor force can also be achieved at the expense of extensive and intensive forms of economic growth. From the point of view of extensiveness, the growth of the means of production is a quantitative condition, and if the commissioning of fixed assets is carried out on the basis of new techniques and by attracting highly skilled workers to production, this process is self-intensive.

In order to achieve sustainable and efficient economic growth, it is essential to define a particular type of economic growth and their combination that allows for the highest results. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the specific features of the climatic, geographical, geopolitical, demographic and social conditions of the country. The appropriateness of the use of one or another type of economic growth in the development of the economy as a whole depends, first of all, on the level of development of the country's productive forces and production relations.

Today, the entire world economy is suffering severely from the coronavirus pandemic. In the early stages of the pandemic, the appropriate scenarios of economic recovery based on various assumptions about how long it would last were further analyzed.

According to the IMF's main forecast scenario, while restrictions on the coronavirus pandemic will remain in place until 2021, they will soften with improvements in treatment therapies and expansion of vaccination coverage, and the acute phase of the pandemic is expected to end by the end of 2022.

International financial institutions, including the World Bank (WB), forecast economic growth in Uzbekistan at 0.6% in 2020 and 6.0% in 2021, while the IMF forecasts growth of 0.7% in 2020 and 5% in 2021. According to estimates, economic growth rates are projected to be 5.1% in 2021. Countries around the world facing the global economic crisis caused by the coronavirus pandemic are using all means and means to mitigate its consequences and get out of the crisis faster. Budget allocations, which make up 10 percent or more of GDP, are aimed at supporting the health care system and combating the pandemic, ensuring a normal life for citizens. In particular, Uzbekistan is implementing comprehensive financial support programs aimed at combating the pandemic and overcoming the negative effects of the global economic crisis. It is known that the Republic of Uzbekistan differs from other Central Asian countries in terms of its natural and climatic conditions, economic potential, the number of labor resources. According to the World Bank, Uzbekistan's proven natural and mineral resources are currently estimated at around \$ 10 trillion. Uzbekistan ranks 14th in the world in terms of natural gas production, 6th in terms of

cotton production, 3rd in terms of cotton exports, 7th in terms of uranium reserves and 7th in terms of gold production.

The demographic situation in the country is characterized by high population growth rates. From 1991 to 2019, the average annual population growth rate averaged 1.7-2.1%, with about 15 million people in the country's population being economically active.

Given the demographic situation in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, the dynamics of the labor force has a positive trend. The number of labor resources increased from 12,594.0 thousand people in 2005 to 18,835.6 thousand people in 2018, or 149.5%. The employment rate in Uzbekistan decreased from 72.3% in 2005 to 70.4% in 2019.

Today, the main problem in the labor market of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to ensure the full and effective inclusive employment of existing labor resources. During this period, the level of economic activity of the population increased from 72.3% to 77.7%. The economic inactivity of the population decreased from 27.7% to 22.3% and the unemployment rate increased from 5.4% to 9.3% (Table 1).

Today, the world economy is characterized by such processes as the intensification of various financial and economic, socio-political crises, the limitation of socio-economic relations between countries as a result of various trade wars between countries. As a result, many national economies around the world are experiencing a slowdown in GDP growth, declining real incomes, deepening social stratification and rising poverty.

Table 1.

The main indicators of the labor market in the Republic of Uzbekistan (annual average)

Indicators	2005y.	2010y.	2015y.	2018y.	2005 in% of change over the year
Labor resources, thousand people	12594.0	16504,2	17663,1	18835,6	149,6
Number of economically active	10196	12286,6	12850,1	14641,7	143,6

population, thousand people					
Level of economic activity of the population, in%	72,3	70,7	70,0	77,7	5,4%
The average annual number of employees in the economy, thousand people	8983,0	11628,4	12223,8	13273,1	147,8
Employment rate, in%	72,0	66,9	66,6	70,4	-1,6
Number of unemployed, thousand people	658,2	658,2	626,3	1368,6	207,9
Unemployment rate, in%	5,4	5,4	4,9	9,3	3,9
Economically inactive population, thousand people	3575,6	4439,4	4714,2	4193,9	117,3
Level of economic inactivity	27,7	25,5	25,7	22,3	-5,4

(passivity),					
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All of the above indicates, on the one hand, that the potential aggregate demand of the population is very high, and, on the other hand, the need to develop an economic policy strategy based on the organization of import-substituting industries that will quickly address the socio-economic problems of the national economy today. shows.

At the same time, the proposed economic policy for the economy of our country, based on the organization of import-substituting industries, should be based on strict restrictions, which are difficult to achieve in one form or another. Given these conditions, it should be noted that in the current situation, the combination of types of economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries, taking into account the specifics of the national economy, is a priority for Uzbekistan to achieve sustainable economic growth.

In the conditions of our country, the combination of types of economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries, taking into account the specifics of the development of industrial and agricultural sectors of the economy, is the most optimal.

Agriculture is one of the most important sectors of the Uzbek economy. This sector is one of the most promising sources of strengthening the export potential, while meeting the needs of the population in food products and the processing industry in raw materials.

According to the research of Russian researchers SG Azikova, GA Bobkov, HH Sokhrokov, an additional 1% increase in agricultural production in developed countries will be 2.5% of industrial infrastructure products, 1% of processing industry products. , 4%, transport services by 0.33%, and sales by 2.7% [12].

Agriculture is the main supplier of products and raw materials for food and light industry, as well as ensuring the country's food and economic security, eliminating the country's dependence on imported food. At the same time, one-fifth of the country's population is employed in agriculture and food industry, while the share of these sectors in the country's GDP is about 23%, and food products account for almost 51% of retail trade turnover. At a time when almost 50% of the population lives in rural areas and 21% in suburban areas, the enterprises of the agro-industrial complex play a crucial role in providing employment. No matter how great the role and importance of agriculture in the country's economy, it is impossible to develop this sector on an extensive basis. Today, the area of irrigated agriculture in the country is 4.3 million hectares, and

pastures and hayfields are just over 21 million hectares, but we can see that the level of arable land and pastures is declining from year to year.

Consistent development of production through deepening of structural changes in agriculture, further strengthening of food security of the country through uninterrupted supply of food products, raw materials to the processing industry, expansion of production of environmentally friendly products, significant increase in export potential of the agricultural sector is one of the most important tasks envisaged.

First of all, by 2020, due to the reduction of 170.5 thousand hectares of cotton and 50 thousand hectares of irrigated grain, 36 thousand hectares of potatoes, 91 thousand hectares of vegetables, 18 thousand hectares of intensive orchards, 50.3 thousand hectares of fodder crops, 14 thousand hectares of oilseeds. and further optimization of arable lands associated with the expansion of vineyards to 11.2 thousand hectares. At the same time, as a result of the use of advanced agricultural technologies, high-yield equipment and machinery and modern methods of irrigation, crop yields increased from 26.1 to 26.9 t / ha (+ 0.8), in cereals from 54.9 to 66, 4 ts / ha (+ 11.5), 218.9 to 230.5 ts / ha (+ 11.6) in potatoes, 277.1 to 294.0 ts / ha (+ 16.9) in vegetables, 123 in fruits, It is planned to increase from 9 to 140.4 ts / ha (+ 16.5), in vineyards from 126.7 to 137.1 ts / ha (+ 10.4) (Table 2).

Table 2.

Forecast indicators for the expansion of agricultural areas and increase production in the country in 2016-2020

Agricultural crops	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2020 y. 2015 y. change
+, -				%			
Area, thousand hectares							
Cotton	1285,5	1255,0	1221,0	1187,0	1151,0	1115,0	-170,5
Cereal grains	1329,5	1329,5	1319,5	1304,5	1289,5	1279,5	-50,0
Potatoes	80,3	85,3	92,5	100,5	108,8	116,3	+ 36,0
Vegetables	192,0	204,6	222,7	243,0	264,0	283,0	+ 91,0
Orcha	261,9	264,4	268,0	272,0	276,1	279,9	+ 18,0

rds								
Forag e crops	309,1	316,1	326,1	337,3	348,9	359,4	+ 50,3	116,3
Oilsee ds	14,3	16,2	19,0	22,1	25,4	28,3	+ 14,0	197,9
Vineya rds	144,0	145,5	147,8	150,3	152,9	155,2	+ 11,2	107,8
Productivity, ts / ha								
Cotton	26,1	26,2	26,3	26,5	26,7	26,9	+ 0,8	103,1
Cereal grains	54,9	60,9	62,5	63,6	65,1	66,4	+ 11,5	120,9
Potato es	218,9	224,3	226,0	227,5	229,0	230,5	+ 11,6	105,3
Vegeta bles	277,1	286,1	288,5	290,0	292,0	294,0	+ 16,9	106,1
Orcha rds	123,9	126,4	129,4	132,9	136,6	140,4	+ 16,5	113,3
Forag e crops	225,0	228,0	231,0	234,0	237,0	240,0	+ 15,0	106,7
Oilsee ds	17,0	18,0	19,0	20,0	21,0	22,0	+ 5,0	129,4
Vineya rds	126,7	127,9	129,9	132,1	134,6	137,1	+ 10,4	108,2
Product production, thousand tons								
Raw cotton	3350	3287	3217	3147	3074	3000	-350,0	89,5
Cereal grains	7305	8100	8250	8300	8400	8500	+ 1 195,0	116,3
Potato es *	2670	2 833	3 010	3206	3411	3601	+ 931,0	134,9
Vegeta bles *	9923	10458	11 031	11651	12314	12925	+ 3002, 2	130,2
Fruits	2731	2874	2 982	3109	3244	3380	+ 648,6	123,8

Food crops *	18 725	18976	19 303	19662	20039	20396	+ 1670,6	108,9
Oilseeds *	98	110	125	132	145	160	+ 62,0	163,3
Grapes	1 556	1 601	1 651	1707	1769	1830	+ 273,9	117,6

931.0 thousand, vegetables - 3,002.2 thousand, fruits - 648.6 thousand and grapes - 273.9 thousand tons. creates the basis for food security.

Table 3.

Forecast indicators for increasing livestock production in the country in 2016-2020

Indexes	2015				Forecast indicators		2020 y. 2015 y. change	
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	+ , -	In %	
Number of livestock, thousand heads								
Cattle	11 635	12 150	12 720	13 350	14 050	14 800	+ 3 165	127,2
Sheep and goats	18 906	19 600	20 380	21 240	22 170	23 187	+ 4 281	122,6
Parranda	60 800	64 600	69 500	75 500	83 000	92 000	+ 31 200	151,3
Livestock production, thousand tons								
Meat (live weight)	1 981	2 060	2 150	2 260	2 375	2 500	+ 519	126,2
Sut	8 823	9 478	10 242	11 075	11 957	13 000	+ 4 177	147,3
Eggs, mln. dona	3 500	6 200	6 900	7 700	8 600	9 600	+ 4 100	274,3
Fish	60	75	90	110	130	150	+ 90	250,0
Honey	9,3	11,0	13,0	15,5	19,0	23,0	+ 13,7	247,3

Modernization and accelerated development of the livestock sector is an important part of the development strategy of the entire agricultural sector. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2015 No PP-2460 "On measures to deepen and develop agricultural reform in 2016-2020" and to increase the number of birds to 31,200,000. As a result, during these years the volume of meat production (live weight) will increase by 519 thousand, milk by 4 177 thousand, fish by 90 thousand, honey by 13.7 thousand tons and eggs by 4 100 million pieces (Table 3).

The availability of natural raw material resources is the most important factor in the development of the economy, especially industry. It is known that the richness of the country's natural resources offers great opportunities for the development of the national economy. The Republic of Uzbekistan is distinguished not only in the region but also in the world by its vast natural resources of chemical raw materials, polymetals and rare ores, precious metals and stones. However, the economic situation in the country is characterized by low employment.

The two-sector model of economic growth developed by A. Lewis clearly reflects the theoretical foundations of intensive agricultural development for the most populous countries. A. Lewis model considers labor reserves as the basis of economic growth. A. Lewis 'two-sector model envisages the redistribution of a portion of the labor force from agriculture to industry and thus the acceleration of economic growth. According to this model, the source of accelerating economic growth in industry is additional labor, which in this case implies an extensive type of economic growth. According to the A. Lewis model, the main source of accelerating economic growth in agriculture is to increase labor productivity, i.e., it is mainly about intensive economic growth. This model has been skillfully applied in a number of countries around the world, taking into account their specific conditions.

Due to the level of development of productive forces, the involvement of natural resources and labor resources in the national economy, the use of the path of extensive development in the industrial sector is a confirmation of our opinion. The level of utilization of production potential in the national economy indicates that the reserves for ensuring the growth of industrial production through the use of existing production capacity are very large.

It should be noted that the sustainable development of the country's economy requires the harmonious development of industry and agriculture.

At the current stage of economic reforms, the industrial sector of the national economy of Uzbekistan, using the extensive factors of economic growth, provides an opportunity to establish import-substituting industries and thus increase the level of economic security.

Ensuring the development of the industrial sector as the basis of economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries implies the development of all types of entrepreneurship in industry. It is the development and expansion of all forms of entrepreneurship that provides ample opportunities for the provision of decent jobs to the unemployed. The development of small and medium business has a special place here.

The priority of small and medium-sized businesses is that they not only provide the initial impetus for the development of the industry, but also eliminate the crisis in the labor market by mobilizing free labor resources. It is known that the development of this industry has laid the foundation for many countries to ensure economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries in the transition period of economic development.

It is known that according to the World Bank's Doing Business ranking published in 2020, the Republic of Uzbekistan ranks 69th out of 190 countries. It should be noted that according to the report of the World Bank, Uzbekistan is currently in the global ranking of "new business support", in the registration of enterprises - 8, in obtaining a building permit - 132, in connection with electricity - 36, in property registration - 72. , 67 places in obtaining loans, 37 places in protection of minority investors, 69 places in taxation, 152 places in international trade, 22 places in enforcement of contracts, 100 places in debt settlement. In recent years, Uzbekistan is among the top ten countries in the world that have achieved the best results in improving the business environment for entrepreneurship.

For the first time, Uzbekistan ranked 92nd out of 152 countries in the world and was included in the CIP index, which measures the competitiveness of the country's processing industry to produce and export goods.

For comparison, the Russian Federation ranks 32nd, Belarus 47th, Kazakhstan 68th, Armenia 103rd, Azerbaijan 120th, Moldova 111th, Kyrgyzstan 122nd and Tajikistan 129th among the CIS countries.

As can be seen from Figure 2 above, although the share of low-tech products in the industrial production of our country is gradually declining, the volume of production of high-tech products does not allow to draw gratifying conclusions.

Thus, in order to effectively stimulate economic growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the organization of import-substituting industries, it is necessary to take measures to ensure the development of the agricultural sector mainly through intensive factors and the industrial sector through extensive factors. In this situation, we can achieve the growth of agricultural production mainly through the consistent implementation of scientific and technological advances and increase the productivity of agricultural land. However, the use of the extensive factor in this important sector cannot be ruled out. It is necessary to increase the number of enterprises engaged in processing, storage and delivery of agricultural products to consumers through the steady increase in agricultural production. However, we must not forget that the intensive factors play a crucial role in the development of the intensive sector, as the extensive factors of development of the agricultural sector are limited.

As for the industrial sector of the national economy, in our opinion, it is expedient to use mainly extensive factors in this area and to apply a partial import substitution strategy. We can explain this by the fact that the development of natural resources in our country is at its starting point. At the same time, increasing employment and reducing poverty will require the full use of existing production capacity, the expansion of industrial production through the establishment of new manufacturing enterprises based on the development of small and medium-sized businesses.

In order to attract more labor resources, it is necessary to increase the level of labor intensity of industrial production growth. At the same time, if the extensive development of the industrial sector is considered as a starting point in the medium term, in the long run it will pave the way for the transition to an intensive type of economic growth. Progressive development testifies that the development of the economy always begins with the use of extensive factors of economic growth, and only then will the transition to an intensive path of development with the full use of the achievements of scientific and technological progress. The transition from the type of extensive growth to the intensive type of economic growth occurs as a result of the law of dialectics, the transition from quantity to quality.

At the current stage of economic reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the use of various combinations of import-substituting forms of economic growth allows the widespread use of the high results achieved in agricultural production in the extensive development of the industrial sector. In the future, this trend will allow the economy of the republic to move from the path of agro-industrial

development, which is strongly dependent on imports, to the industrial-agrarian path of development, which will allow the organization of import-substituting industries. This is one of the important aspects of the sustainable development of the national economy, which will serve to further strengthen the economic and political independence of our country in the current uncertainty in the world economy.

Defining targets is an important step in defining forms of industrial policy based on import-substituting production. Based on the aspects considered on the nature of import substitution, several target areas can be identified: first, import substitution programs can be implemented to ensure a positive trade balance; second, it can be implemented in order to strengthen the economic security of the country; third, import substitution can be done in order to stimulate the development of domestic producers and help increase their competitiveness; fourth, import substitution can be done to reduce the level of dependence on imports; fifth, import substitution can be done as an emergency measure to fill the domestic market with certain goods under various sanctions imposed on the country. At the current stage of economic reforms and the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, we can include the prevention of declining production rates, filling the domestic market with quality consumer goods, preventing disruptions in the supply chain.

Conclusions and recommendations

Concluding the review of the methodological basis of economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries, we can note the following:

First, a review of the methodological content of import substitution and, on this basis, the definition of its forms will allow to determine its optimal directions for the country at the current stage of economic reforms. In practice, it is too early to talk about secondary import substitution in the context of the long-lasting transformational crisis of production and the country's high dependence on imports. Although Uzbekistan has huge reserves of production resources and reserves, their use is still at an early stage. Therefore, the use of foreign production factors (which is especially evident in the involvement of foreign production equipment and technologies) in the use of import substitution strategies cannot be ruled out. Moreover, without protectionist measures, it is not possible to carry out the initial stages of the application of import substitution. In addition, we believe that economic growth based on the organization of import-substituting industries under the influence of economic

law, which represents the transition from quantitative growth to qualitative indicators, will later have an intensive characterization.

Second, at the current stage of economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in terms of the level of import coverage, partial import substitution is acceptable, and in terms of the use of production resources - primary import substitution. This is explained by the stagnation and economic obsolescence of production techniques, which were observed at the beginning of economic reforms. In such circumstances, it would not be logical to talk about secondary import substitution. In the context of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is desirable to stimulate import-substituting economic growth through the intensive development of agriculture and industry. Therefore, when using the import substitution strategy for the development of sectors of the national economy, it is necessary to take into account the widespread use of the latest production equipment and technologies that meet international standards and serve to ensure the competitiveness of domestic goods.

The main goals in the implementation of the import substitution program in the Republic of Uzbekistan are to ensure a positive trade balance, strengthen the economic security of the country, stimulate the development of local producers, reduce dependence on imports. Third, a comprehensive approach to import substitution allows for the stimulation of the reproduction function, which determines the volume and proportions of expanded reproduction. At the same time, appropriate conditions will be created to increase production, encouraging the satisfaction of the growing needs of the population through import substitution. It should be noted that a comprehensive approach to import substitution will ensure the conversion of natural and other resources into material goods consumed by society through the introduction of reproduction processes.

Fourth, the practical use of socially complex import substitution means raising living standards and improving the material well-being of all segments of the population. In general, the complexity of import substitution is usually characterized by its social orientation, which provides for a new quality of economic growth, which in turn requires that economic growth is inextricably linked to the well-being of the population and the two processes need to be coordinated.

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